

Newsletter 09/2018

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Dissemination and Upcoming Events: Meet Us!

ESIWACE will participate in

- 18th ECMWF Workshop on High Performance Computing in Meteorology, 24-28 Sep, Reading/UK, www.ecmwf.int/en/learning/workshops
- eScience 2018, session Weather & Climate Science in the Digital Era, 31 Oct, Amsterdam/Netherlands, <https://www.escience2018.com/page/471838>
- ICT 2018: Imagine Digital – Connect Europe, 4-6 Dec, Vienna/Austria, <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/events/ict-2018-imagine-digital-connect-europe>
- Supercomputing, 11-16 Nov, Dallas/USA, <http://sc18.supercomputing.org/>

Deliverables and milestone documents referred to in the newsletters can be downloaded from Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>) and from the ESIWACE website, section Results (<https://www.esiwace.eu/results/deliverables> and <https://www.esiwace.eu/results/milestones>).

ESiWACE2 and IS-ENES3: The Story Continues...

The proposals for the centre of excellence (CoE) ESiWACE2 and the infrastructure project IS-ENES3, submitted to the 2018 calls on CoEs and research infrastructures by the European Commission, have been selected for funding and are both in the grant preparation phase. While IS-ENES3 is mostly aimed at providing the infrastructure to efficiently support the European climate community in its participation in international intercomparison modelling experiments, particularly for the next IPCC report, and manifold exploitation of their results – thus serving sciences and society – ESiWACE2 will concentrate on the many computing challenges which the next-generation climate- and weather-models have to face to fully benefit from future exascale architectures.

Official title: Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe, Phase 2

Acronym: ESiWACE2

Coordination: J. Biercamp (DKRZ)

Start date: 1 January 2019

Budget: 8 million Euro

ESiWACE2 brings together 20 partners from 9 European countries and plans to further push Earth System Model technology towards execution on upcoming pre-exascale and exascale systems, focusing on the preparation of production-ready, community model-based ESM simulation systems. These developments will be complemented by the establishment of new technologies such as domain-specific languages, tools to minimise data output for ensemble runs, and services to the community in terms of performance optimisation support. Co-design between model developers, HPC manufacturers and HPC centres is to be fostered, in particular through the design and employment of High-Performance Climate and Weather benchmarks, with the first version of these benchmarks feeding into ESiWACE2 through the research project ESCAPE-2.

IS-ENES3 is the third phase of the distributed e-infrastructure of ENES, as the European climate modelling community faces the challenges of CMIP6. IS-ENES3 will develop, document and deploy new and advanced models and tools, standards and services to deal with unprecedented data volumes and model complexity; it will stimulate collaboration, disseminate software and data, and further integrate the community. IS-ENES3 will support climate research, climate impact science, and climate services; it will ease access and exploitation of data and knowledge produced by state-of-the-art models. In doing so, the project will find innovative ways of working with the Copernicus programme, with other parts of the European data infrastructure, and with the HPC and data analytics industries in synergy with ESiWACE2. IS-ENES3 comprises 22 partners from 11 countries and is planned to start on 1 December 2018.

EuroHPC

EuroHPC is the European exascale programme. It is aiming to acquire large pre-exascale machines in 2020 with exascale machines in 2022/23 including substantial European technology contributions. The EuroHPC programme is supported by 22 European countries (see <http://eurohpc.eu/>).

EuroHPC launched three working groups last spring, to prepare reports and propositions on (i) Architectures, (ii) Benchmarking, and (iii) Users requirements. The CoEs were invited to represent their communities in all three working groups, and to potentially provide relevant benchmarks. For the weather and climate community, the CoE ESiWACE involved the ENES HPC-Task Force to actively contribute to these three reports.

5th ENES HPC Workshop in Lecce

The 5th ENES HPC workshop was held on 17-18 May in Lecce, Italy with 49 participants. The main focus of the workshop, organised and supported through ESIWACE and building on the previous ENES HPC workshops (Lecce, 2011; Toulouse, 2013; Hamburg, 2014 and Toulouse, 2016), was on high-resolution modelling. It also addressed other issues such as domain-specific languages, coupling & I/O tools and involved discussions about European and international HPC eco-systems and data centre support, as well as the relationship with the EC strategy on HPC, featuring invited speakers from EXDCI, PoP, EoCoE, EuroEXA.

Workshop attendees; picture credits: CMCC

More details on the workshop can be found in ESIWACE deliverable D1.5 and on the ESIWACE website: <https://www.esiwace.eu/events/5th-enes-hpc-workshop/presentations>

Hackathon for High-Resolution DYAMOND Data

On 20-21 August, a hackathon night was organised at the Max-Planck-Institute for Meteorology, supported by ESIWACE and corresponding members, to have first looks into the unprecedented high-resolution DYAMOND data. The post-processing and analysis scripts will represent an input for the planned in-place processing of the DYAMOND data that shall be set up in near future.

Information on the DYAMOND project can be found at: <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/dyiamond>

More information on the hackathon can be found at:

https://www.mpimet.mpg.de/en/communication/news/single-news/news/erster-hack-a-thon-am-mpi-m/?tx_news_pi1%5Bcontroller%5D=News&tx_news_pi1%5Baction%5D=detail&cHash=0dc8b7d54ebcf19be872be246d4e5b17

picture credits: MPI-M

Towards Compression for Ensemble Simulations

Three new data compression methods to store model output of ensemble simulations have been investigated to cope with the data avalanche of high-resolution simulations. The data compression methods allow a reduction of the number of bits that is used to store each variable within model output data, resulting in a reduction of up to one third of the overall data volume. Using the new methods, the loss of information is much smaller when the number of bits is reduced when compared to the loss of information for conventional data compression methods. However, savings that can be achieved will be different for different model fields.

The most successful methods that have been considered are using similarities of ensemble members to reduce the number of bits per variable with minimal loss of information. These methods link numerical precision to ensemble spread to provide high precision for model variables that can be predicted with low uncertainty (small ensemble spread) and low precision for model variables that show large uncertainties (large ensemble spread). Details on the methods are described in ESIWACE deliverable D2.7 and particularly in:

P.D. Dueben, M. Leutbecher, P. Bauer (2018). New methods for data storage of model output from ensemble simulations, submitted.

The XIOS-endpoint Library

The developments and optimisation accomplished for the XIOS library during the last 24 months, partly supported through ESIWACE, are described in ESIWACE deliverable D2.4.

The most important improvement, which will be available to users in the next release XIOS-3 which is planned for summer 2019, is the extension of XIOS parallel efficiency by adding multithreading capacity. The idea of the multithreaded interface implemented in XIOS comes from the MPI proposal brought up during the last MPI Forums: the concept of MPI endpoints.

An endpoint interface was implemented in XIOS. In this interface, OpenMP threads act in the same manner as MPI processes, adding a second level of parallelism without major modification to the XIOS library. The resulting library, which keeps all the functionalities of the single-threaded XIOS library and can be easily branched to scientific models with a hybrid MPI/OpenMP parallelism, is called the XIOS-endpoint. XIOS-endpoint has been validated with multiple tests. The performance was analysed, in a first step, with the real LMDz atmospheric model. The results show that XIOS-endpoint reduces the time spent in the LMDZ XIOS client part by 10-16% depending on the workflow density. Although these performance results are very preliminary, they give confidence in the XIOS multithreading newly-developed capacity.

A Performance Analysis Exercise and Code Optimisation in NEMO

The Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean (NEMO) has been used as an example for analysing and solving an MPI communication problem. In the analysis exercise, it is shown how to answer the questions of where, why and what is degrading model's scalability, and how this information can help developers in finding solutions that will mitigate their eventual issues. This work also demonstrates how performance analysis carried out with small size experiments, using limited resources, can lead to optimisations that will impact bigger experiments running on thousands of cores, making it easier to deal with the exascale challenge. More details can be found in:

O. Tintó Prims, M. Castrillo, M.C. Acosta, O. Mula-Valls, A. Sanchez Lorente, K. Serradell, A. Cortés, F.J. Doblas-Reyes (2018). Finding, analysing and solving MPI communication bottlenecks in Earth System models. *Journal of Computational Science*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jocs.2018.04.015>.

Besides, focusing on a simplified configuration "BENCH" of NEMO (ocean physics and dynamics, excluding sea-ice and I/O, and weakly forcing a simplified rectangular pool to modulate or switch off communication), modules could be isolated and their performances could be investigated separately. Applying a new set of instrumentation within NEMO and using this simplified configuration, a better picture of scalability variations with resolution or machine is now available, and it is even possible to clarify their origin. MPI communication optimisation is work in progress. Some kernel optimisations have been proposed that improve global performance of NEMO by about 9%. Current and future work focuses on MPI datatype optimisation, shared MPI implementation and loop tiling.

More details can be found in ESIWACE deliverable D2.2.

EC-Earth Optimisations

The coupling between the two main components of EC-Earth, the ocean component (NEMO) and the atmospheric component (IFS), has been evaluated, using OASIS3-MCT as coupler. The results show that the coupling could represent an important bottleneck (up to 50% of the time step of IFS) of the execution if a global conservation operation, combined with a large number of parallel processes and a high coupling frequency, is applied to the coupling fields without activating the optimisation options.

Two options available in OASIS3-MCT have been evaluated and were found to improve the coupling configuration. These options can reduce the coupling cost by more than 90%. The first one optimises the field exchanges between components and minimises the interpolation and communication process. The second one shows that OASIS3-MCT is able to reduce the MPI overhead by using global communications instead of one-to-all/all-to-one communications and by removing the serial calculations done by default on the master process.

A reproducibility test was done to evaluate the two optimisations. The test proved that the significant differences are less than 1%, comparing the simulation results of one-year experiments, using the default configuration and both optimisations (together and separately).

More details can be found in ESIWACE deliverable D2.2 and in:

M.C. Acosta, X. Yepes-Arbós, S. Valcke, E. Maisonave, K. Serradell, O. Mula-Valls, F.J. Doblas-Reyes (2016). Performance analysis of EC-Earth 3.2: Coupling. BSC-CES Technical Memorandum 2016-006

Employing the Earth System Data Middleware

The Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM) has been designed to allow interactions with different kinds of backend, by means of data storing and retrieval. Specifically, the ESDM allows interactions with various backends, exploiting different specific plugins to enable connection and I/O operations on different storage types. The design targets, but is not limited to, earth system data, addressing the challenges faced by domain scientists and data centre operators for usability and performance. The architecture builds on top of NetCDF and HDF5 but utilises scientific metadata to harness a data structure centric perspective while retaining well-established end-user interfaces.

Prototype capability of ESDM has been demonstrated and performance has been assessed in various deployments. For example, at STFC (JASMIN), throughput rates of 492/290 MiB/s and 4006/1340 MiB/s were achieved (read/write) using 1 node and 16 nodes (4 processes per node). At DKRZ (Mistral, Lustre02 file system), a performance of 200/150 GB/s (read/write) was achieved on 200 nodes. Additional runs of the ESDM benchmarks were conducted in a configuration where data was stored on both Lustre file systems at DKRZ concurrently. In that case, performance of the write path could be increased to 220 GiB/s, but the read performance was reduced. A reason is the current prototypical implementation of the metadata handling. Further tests have been conducted at CMCC, considering ESDM performance in read/write mode on the Athena HPC cluster over GPFS (ESDM POSIX mode) and over the WOS cluster, running ESDM on OphidiaLab (ESDM WOS mode). Besides, a first version of the Clovis backend has been implemented, and detailed performance evaluation is in progress.

More details can be found in the ESIWACE report for milestone 9.

A Prototype Tape Library JDMA for Advanced Tape Subsystems

The development of a multi-tiered storage library is motivated by the fragmenting of storage systems that are now in use at data centres and, more specifically, the wide range in latency when recovering data from these devices. Users wishing to store or retrieve data on these systems are confronted by a heterogeneous array of tools with different workflows.

Therefore, new software has been developed, consisting of a multi-tiered storage library which provides a single API to users to move data to a number of different storage systems, query the data that they have stored on those systems, and retrieve the data. These interactions are carried out using a common user interface, which is a command line tool to be used interactively, and an HTTP API to be used programmatically. The command line tool essentially provides a wrapper for calls to the HTTP API.

The source code for the multi-tiered storage library can be downloaded from: https://github.com/cedadev/django-jdma_control/releases/tag/0.1.6

The library has been designed for deployment at any site, but in order to provide focus, it is being piloted at JASMIN where it will enter production in the near future. For this reason, it is known as the JASMIN Data Migration Application (henceforth JDMA). While the initial purpose was to move data from POSIX disk to tape, many features have been added.

Details on the software are listed in the ESIWACE report for milestone 8.

Revised Version: Handbook for System Administrators

The next version of the *Handbook for System Administrators: Specification of a standard recommendation for an ESM System Software Stack* has been prepared. This version will be available on the ESIWACE website (www.esiwace.eu). It is the final version supported through ESIWACE.

The handbook contains:

- Revised requirements that ESM workflows pose to HPC environments, as well as recommendations and best practices to fulfil them;
- a list of the system software that is common for ESM workflows;
- a description of tools that allow for automation of the system software deployment.

This document shall also become a starting point for collaboration between users and system administrators. The former are expected to refer to this document to get indications on what problems need to be solved and what questions need to be posed to fill the gap between the system software stack that is available on the system they use and the (modelling) software stack that is necessary to run their experiments. The latter are asked to check out our recommendations and help to improve this handbook where useful.

The updated handbook can be found at:

https://www.esiwace.eu/results/misc/handbook-for-system-administrators/at_download/file

Snapshots

DKRZ and partners have recently prepared a manuscript on performance analysis and modelling of global high-resolution, atmosphere-only simulation. DKRZ currently supports MPI-M at carrying out DYAMOND runs with the ICON model at 2.5km global resolution and is in contact with other ICON developers from MPI-M on high-resolution, coupled atmosphere-ocean simulations.

Researchers at ECMWF have investigated [challenges and design choices for global weather and climate models based on machine learning](#).

BSC computational researchers have been running T1279-ORCA12 EC-Earth 3.2 configuration in Mare Nostrum 4 with more than ten thousand cores and tuning the execution to take advantage of new Intel core features and Intel Omni-Path Architecture.

Bull is currently working on NEMO in collaboration with IPSL and the NEMO HPC working group, focussing on the BENCH configuration to improve its scalability.

The Met Office continues to develop Cylc and is now planning the major upgrade to Python 3 and a move to a new web based GUI framework. This work will take us into future H2020 projects and wider investment from a growing Cylc development community.

A new official version of the OASIS coupler, OASIS3-MCT_4.0, was released last July and is available on OASIS3-MCT web site (<http://oasis.enes.org>) . This new version specifically includes, in particular, a hybrid MPI+OpenMP parallelisation of the SCRIP library leading to great reduction in the offline calculation time of the remapping weights, and a new communication method, using the remapping weights to define the intermediate mapping decomposition, offering a significant gain at run time.

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